

Robot-Assisted Training to Enhance Emotional Well-Being and Independence Skills in Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder

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Abstract

Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) often face challenges in achieving independence in daily living activities, particularly in academic and social settings. While state of the art therapies focus on foundational social and cognitive skills, there is a gap in interventions targeting real-world application, such as managing stress in school-related scenarios. This study explores the feasibility and potential efficacy of a robot-assisted training protocol designed for adolescents with ASD to foster cognitive and emotional resilience in managing stressful daily life situations. The intervention combined standard therapy with robot-mediated sessions, simulating real-world challenges like oral exams. Participants engaged in the oral exam simulation with the humanoid robot iCub across eight structured sessions. Quantitative assessments included standardized tests evaluating reading comprehension, attention and executive functioning, cognitive flexibility, and emotional well-being. Qualitative observations were also collected during oral exam simulations. While the results did not reach conventional statistical significance, a promising trend emerged in the reduction of anxiety and depression symptoms in the robot-assisted group. Qualitative data revealed high engagement, curiosity, and positive attitudes toward the robot, with minimal therapist intervention required. These findings suggest that robot-assisted training may offer a feasible and engaging approach to support emotional resilience in adolescents with ASD.

Introduction

Adolescents with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) often face significant challenges in achieving independence in daily living activities, particularly in high-pressure academic and social settings. While traditional therapeutic approaches have been effective in developing foundational social and cognitive skills, they do not address directly preparation of adolescents

for the real-world application of these competencies (Hume, 2014). Specifically, evidence-based practices targeting academic or pre-academic performance, self-help abilities, and vocational readiness remain limited especially for adolescents and young adults with ASD (Hume et al., 2021). This gap highlights the need for innovative interventions that can bridge the divide between clinical training and independence in everyday lives for this population.

Social robotics has emerged as a particularly promising intervention approach, building on substantial evidence of effectiveness with children with ASD. Research has demonstrated that social robots can significantly improve core developmental areas in children with ASD, including socio-emotional development, communication and interaction skills, and cognitive functioning (Hume et al., 2021; Alabdulkareem et al., 2022). Robot-mediated interventions have consistently shown effectiveness in eliciting prosocial behaviors such as joint attention, imitation, and eye contact while reducing stereotyped behaviors and enhancing spontaneous language use (Diehl et al., 2012; Bartl-Pokorny et al., 2021; for a review see Ghiglini & Wykowska, 2026). The success of these child-focused interventions stems from robots' capacity to provide predictable, simplified social cues that reduce sensory and emotional overstimulation, which is a common barrier in traditional therapeutic settings for individuals with ASD (Scassellati et al., 2012; Kumazaki et al., 2020; Ghiglini et al., 2023).

However, despite this accumulating evidence, analogous applications for adolescents and young adults remain largely underexplored (Kouroupa et al., 2022). Adolescence represents a critical phase characterized by heightened expectations for maturing into independence and the growing need for autonomous functioning. Recent studies have begun to extend robot-assisted approaches into these higher-order socio-cognitive domains, demonstrating that robot-mediated interactions can enhance self-confidence and communication skills in young adults with ASD (Kumazaki et al., 2019). Moreover, individuals with social anxiety, which is a common comorbidity in ASD, report reduced physiological stress when interacting with robots compared to humans (Rasouli et al., 2022). The unique advantages of social robots for adolescent populations lie in their capacity to simulate real-world social pressures in a controlled, non-judgmental environment. Humanoid robots, with their human-like morphology and gestures, appear to be particularly effective in fostering engagement in young adults, potentially facilitating better skill generalization to human interactions (Manzi et al., 2021). This is especially relevant for contexts like academic evaluation, job interviews, or oral examinations—situations that demand both cognitive performance and emotional regulation under social scrutiny. Social robots can provide the structured, predictable feedback essential for skill development while being non-intimidating and maintaining the ecological validity necessary for real-world transfer.

Building on this foundation, the present study investigated the feasibility and efficacy of a robot-assisted training protocol, designed to enhance cognitive skills and emotional resilience in adolescents with ASD during stressful daily life situations. The intervention combined standard therapy with robot-mediated sessions that simulate a real-world challenge, such as an oral exam at school, which is a potentially stress-inducing academic scenario. Participants engaged with a humanoid robot across eight structured sessions using original comics as study materials, designed to practice both content mastery and social-emotional regulation skills essential for academic success.

To evaluate the impact of the robot-assisted training, we compared, with standardized clinical tests, participants who received the robot-based sessions with those who underwent standard therapy alone. In addition to quantitative outcome measures, qualitative observations were collected to capture participants' engagement and interaction patterns during the oral exam simulations. Quantitative assessments included standardized tests evaluating: the ability to understand and process written information (Prove MT-3 Clinica, Reading Comprehension subtest; Cornoldi et al.), a critical skill for academic success; attention and executive functioning (NEPSY-II Design Fluency subtest; Korkman et al., 2007); cognitive flexibility, (Wisconsin Card Sorting Test - WCST; Heaton et al., 1981); emotional well-being (Test for Anxiety and Depression in Childhood and Adolescence - TAD; Newcomer, Barenbaum, & Bryant, 1995).

We hypothesized that incorporating a humanoid robot into standard therapy would provide a feasible and engaging approach to support adolescents in developing competences essential for independent living. Therefore, the primary focus of this study was to evaluate the practicality and acceptability of using an embodied robotic agent as a complementary tool in a clinical setting for adolescents, with quantitative comparisons providing insight into its relative effectiveness. By demonstrating the protocol's feasibility, we aim to lay the groundwork for future research exploring the potential of robot-assisted interventions to enhance autonomy-related skills in adolescents with ASD.

Methods

Participants

For each participant involved in the study, parents or legal guardians provided written informed consent following a thorough explanation of the study's design, methods, and objectives. The training with the robot included twenty-two participants (Mean Age = 12.86 ± 1.21, Mean IQ = 82.35 ± 11.64, with 4 females). Each participant had a confirmed diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) issued by the Italian National Health Care System (Servizio Sanitario Nazionale, SSN), which was further validated through the Autism Diagnostic Interview-Revised (ADI-R) and the Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule – Second Edition (ADOS-2) by specialized clinicians at Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione (Centro Boggiano Pico). All procedures complied with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki and were approved by the Regional Ethics Committee of Liguria (Comitato Etico Regione Liguria). The selection process ensured no discrimination based on race, ethnicity, gender identity, or socioeconomic background. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions: an experimental group receiving robot-assisted intervention in addition to standard therapy (n = 11; 4 females; Mean Age = 12.54 ± 0.69 years, Mean IQ = 81.55 ± 10.02), and a control group receiving standard therapy alone (n = 11; 0 females; Mean Age = 13.18 ± 1.54 years, Mean IQ = 83.08 ± 13.01). Standard therapy was based on Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) principles and other evidence-based practices aligned with national guidelines.

Setup

All sessions took place in a room at the clinical center (Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione (Centro Boggiano Pico) where participants were seated at a table facing the humanoid robot iCub (Metta et al., 2010). The robot was positioned behind a transparent plexiglass

barrier for safety, with a central hole that allowed a small wheeled tray to pass training props between participants and the robot during the interaction (see Figure 1). The training props consisted in a total of four soft cubes used to represent school subjects. For each session, four images of the comic covers used for training were also placed on the plexiglass as the robot would use them to select each session's topic (for full description of the training, see Robot-assisted training section below). The robot was operated in Wizard-of-Oz mode by a research assistant, with support from an LLM (Large Language Model; ChatGPT, OpenAI, 2025) integrated into the protocol to provide information restricted to the comic content, while a clinician sat beside the participant to monitor comfort and ensure alignment with therapeutic goals.

Figure 1. Training setup featuring the humanoid robot iCub. The robot is positioned behind a plexiglass barrier on which four exemplary comic cover images are placed (two per school subject). The small tray (in white) is on the participants side of the table, as the four soft cubes with stickers (corresponding to the four school subjects) used in the training.

The comics

Participants studied eight short (10-page) comics, designed specifically for this protocol, covering four school subjects over 8 sessions. The first four sessions covered Literature and Technology, while the remaining four focused on Science and History. Within each subject, two topics were assigned. This division allowed for a balanced exposure to both humanistic and scientific subjects, mirroring the school programs of Italian middle school and early years of high school. Each comic was framed as a chapter of “*The Adventures of iCub*”, featuring the robot and a young protagonist exploring school topics in an engaging format (for an example, see Figure 2). All comics were curated by an illustrator, and the content was revised by the research team at the Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia and the clinical therapists at the Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione (Centro Boggiano Pico).

Figure 2. Example of the comic of one of the topics of Technology: *Means of Transport*. On the left is the cover and on the right is the comic original content where iCub takes a young boy on a journey through time, exploring the history of transportation.

Robot-assisted training

The robot-assisted training protocol was jointly developed by the research team at the Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia and the therapists of the clinical centre Piccolo Cottolengo Genovese di Don Orione (Centro Boggiano Pico) involved in the study, within the framework of the ERC-funded Proof-of-Concept RONIN project (RObot traINing INdependence). Before starting the actual sessions with the robot, participants were briefed on the task and given all comics. They were instructed to choose between the first two assigned subjects, while iCub would select one of the two topics within that subject on the oral “exam” day. This ensured participants focused on a maximum of two topics per session.

Each session started with iCub greeting the participant and then requesting the cube representing the chosen subject. The participant passed the cube through the plexiglass via the wheeled tray. After inspecting the cube, iCub shared a fun fact about the chosen subject (e.g. “*Did you know...?*”) to ease the first moments of the “exam”. The robot then selected a topic for the exam by pointing to the corresponding comic cover image on the plexiglass.

To ensure flexibility and adapt to the children’s varying levels of preparation, the sessions were tailored by the operator to each participant’s readiness. Prepared participants, who could summarize the comic content, were asked specific questions (e.g., the name of a character in the comic). Less prepared participants received open-ended prompts (e.g., “*How does the comic start?*”) or were encouraged to reference the comic during the exam. Finally, in cases where a participant was prepared for the other topic (i.e. not the one requested by iCub), the session would refocus on that topic to maintain engagement with the “exam”. This approach ensured that all participants could engage meaningfully, regardless of their preparation level, while still maintaining the integrity of the exam simulation.

To stimulate participants’ ability to shift focus and re-engage during the exam across sessions, which we thought would support training executive functions, interruptions performed by the robot were incorporated into four sessions. These interruptions included questions about time

(“*What time is it?*”), weather (“*How’s the weather today?*”), objects in the room (“*What type of flowers are on the shelf?*”), and holidays (“*How many days are left until Christmas/Easter?*” - depending on the season when the training happened). Each interruption began with the robot saying, “*Excuse me...*”. For less prepared participants, interruptions were either omitted or rescheduled. At the end of each session, the robot provided participants with feedback about their performance (see Figure 3). Each session lasted between 10 and 15 minutes.

Figure 3. First-person point of view interaction with iCub during the training. The robot gives a positive feedback (such as “thumbs up” gesture) at the end of the session.

Measures of interest

Participants completed a neuropsychological assessment to evaluate cognitive and functional effects of the training at two time points: T0 (baseline) and T1 (post-intervention). The assessment encompassed the following standardized clinical tests:

The subtest Reading Comprehension from the Prove MT-3 Clinica battery (Cornoldi et al., 2016) was used to evaluate written text comprehension abilities. This test consists of multiple-choice questions related to two texts that differ in characteristics and content—such as length, complexity, and format—tailored to the participants' school grade. The dependent variable measured is the total number of correct answers. This test was chosen to assess whether the training with iCub improved participants' ability to understand and process written information, a critical skill for academic success.

The NEPSY-II (Korkman et al., 2007) Design Fluency subtest, part of the attention and executive functioning domain, which encompasses sustained attention, planning, cognitive flexibility, monitoring, and rule adherence. This subtest assesses the ability to produce different drawings by connecting up to five dots, presented in two arrays: structured and random. The dependent variable is the number of drawings generated on each array within a specified time limit. This subtest was included to measure improvements in executive functions, particularly cognitive flexibility and planning, which are essential for academic performance and daily living skills.

The Wisconsin Card Sorting Test (WCST; Heaton et al., 1981) is a neuropsychological test frequently employed to evaluate cognitive flexibility in studies of executive functions, including in individuals with ASD (Hill, 2004). In this test, participants sort cards based on implicit rules

(e.g., color, shape, number) that change after 10 consecutive correct responses, requiring them to update their strategies. Key metrics used to evaluate improvement across study periods include perseverative responses and errors—when responders fail to update the rule despite negative feedback—which are considered an indicator of difficulties in cognitive flexibility (Landry & Al-Taie, 2016). This test was chosen to assess participants' ability to adapt and shift cognitive strategies, a crucial executive function that impacts learning and problem-solving.

The Test for Anxiety and Depression in Childhood and Adolescence (TAD; Newcomer, Barenbaum, & Bryant, 1995) was employed to measure variations in anxiety and depression after the training. The self-report questionnaire (Scale A) comprises 22 items: 11 items assess depressive symptoms, and 11 items assess anxious symptoms. The TAD uses a 4-point Likert-type scale indicating the frequency and severity of each item, with responses ranging from “never” to “often”. This test was selected to evaluate the impact of the training on participants' emotional well-being, specifically anxiety and depression levels, which are common comorbidities in individuals with ASD (Hollocks et al., 2014).

Qualitative observations

Alongside the clinical tests, qualitative observations of participants' engagement, responsiveness, and adaptability during the robot-mediated oral exams provided deeper insights into their progress. These observations were collected by the robot operator and therapists during the training sessions.

All participants expressed a positive attitude toward the robot, and a few even imitated its movements, showing curiosity and engagement. Some integrated school-learned knowledge into their responses, expanding on the assigned topics with additional details, which reflected genuine participation and motivation. The robot's planned interruptions (e.g., questions about time or weather) initially elicited surprise but were generally well managed; most participants responded politely and smoothly resumed the main conversation. While the majority felt confident and prepared for each session, two participants did not complete the required comic preparation, resulting in more limited verbal exchanges, and two expressed mild anxiety, particularly when uncertain about their answers.

To quantify therapist support during the exam simulation, we collected the number of therapist prompts needed in each session (see Figure 4). A prompt was defined as any intervention required to help a participant complete the session. Overall, participants needed minimal support and showed acquisition of training autonomy over time, suggesting that the robot's consistent and non-judgmental behavior helped sustain the interaction and maintain engagement across varying levels of readiness.

Figure 4. Average number of therapist’s prompts per session across all participants. The x-axis shows the chronological sequence of the training sessions. The y-axis indicates the count of prompts provided to each participant per session. Seven participants received at least one prompt over the sessions, and four did not receive any. The overall pattern shows a general decrease in the average number of prompts as the sessions progressed.

Data Analysis

To account for the substantial heterogeneity in ASD phenotypic expression and reduce the influence of confounding baseline variability, the primary dependent variable in all analyses was operationalized as intra-individual change scores (Δ), computed as the difference between consecutive time points ($T1 - T0$) for each standardized clinical measure (Prove MT-3, NEPSY-II, WCST and TAD). Given the non-normal distribution of Δ values we adopted Mann-Whitney U tests for between-group comparisons. This non-parametric procedure was selected due to its robustness to violations of normality and its reliance on rank-ordered data, which provides a more valid estimate of central tendency than parametric tests when sample sizes are constrained ($n < 30$ per group). The rank-based methodology mitigates the distorting effects of outliers and skewed distributions, thereby enhancing the reliability of inferential conclusions.

Statistical analyses were conducted in JASP Version 0.96.0 (JASP Team, 2026). For each comparison, we report the exact U statistic, two-tailed p-values, and the rank-biserial correlation (r) as a standardized effect size metric, supplemented by 95% confidence intervals (CIs) to quantify precision. This analytical framework ensures that findings are evaluated not only for statistical significance but also for clinical meaningfulness and replicability, addressing both Type I error control and effect magnitude.

Results

For the TAD, the test statistic was $U = 94.00$, with a rank-biserial correlation of $r = 0.424$ ($p = .071$, 95% CI [-0.030, 0.733]), indicating a medium-to-large effect size that did not reach conventional level of significance. This pattern suggests a trend toward reduced anxiety in the robot-assisted training group relative to the control group. The NEPSY-II Design Fluency subscale yielded $U = 48.00$, $r = -0.273$ ($p = .257$, 95% CI [-0.642, 0.200]), suggesting a non-significant small-to-medium negative effect with wide confidence intervals crossing zero. Similarly, the MT-3 showed $U = 50.50$, $r = -0.235$ ($p = .342$, 95% CI [-0.618, 0.239]), again with a non-significant, small negative effect. As per the WCST, neither perseverative answers ($U = 56.50$, $r = -0.058$, $p = .843$, 95% CI [-0.503, 0.411]) nor perseverative errors ($U = 57.50$, $r = -0.042$, $p = .895$, 95% CI [-0.491, 0.425]) differed between groups, with negligible effect sizes. In all cases, the standard error of the rank-biserial correlation was 0.241, reflecting the limited precision of effect size estimates due to the small sample size ($n = 11$ per group). While the TAD approached significance with a trend favoring the robot-assisted group (Figure 5), the confidence intervals for all measures included zero, precluding definitive conclusions.

Figure 5. Left panel: Mean TAD scores at baseline (T0) and post-intervention (T1) for the control group (open circles) and the iCub robot-assisted intervention group (closed circles), with error bars representing ± 1 standard error of the mean (SEM). Higher numbers indicate more anxiety symptoms. Right panel: Estimated mean change (Δ) in TAD scores from T0 to T1 for each group, with SEM error bars. Positive delta scores indicate more symptoms at T1 compared to T0. Visual inspection suggests a reduction in anxiety scores following robot-assisted therapy, whereas the control group exhibits minimal change. However, these observations should be interpreted with caution and require validation in larger cohorts.

Discussion

The present study explored the feasibility and preliminary efficacy of a robot-assisted training protocol designed to foster cognitive and emotional resilience in adolescents with ASD. Although quantitative analyses did not yield statistically significant differences between groups, a trend toward reduced anxiety and depressive symptoms was observed in the robot-assisted condition (TAD scores). This pattern suggests that robot-mediated interventions may positively influence emotional well-being, in the context of stressful daily life situations, which is a critical outcome for supporting adolescents with ASD during their transition to adulthood.

Both the structure of the training and qualitative observations support the intervention's therapeutic potential. The qualitative data revealed consistent engagement, curiosity, and positive attitudes toward the robot, aligning with extensive literature showing that humanoid robots provide predictable, non-judgmental interactions particularly beneficial for individuals with ASD (Kouroupa et al., 2022; Kumazaki et al., 2020, Ghiglino & Wykowska, 2026). The iCub robot's human-like morphology and expressive capabilities likely facilitated this engagement while maintaining the simplified social cues that reduce sensory overstimulation (Scassellati et al., 2012; Alabdulkareem et al., 2022). This is in line with Ghiglino et al. (2025) who reported that iCub-based role-playing sessions significantly improved social understanding and adaptive communication in children with ASD, likely due to the robot's unique combination of human-like embodiment and programmable structure, which allows it to deliver interactions that are simultaneously predictable, socially expressive, and dynamically adaptable to each participant's responses.

The positive engagement with the training occurred alongside demanding cognitive tasks: sessions required participants to manage sustained verbal interactions, respond to thematic questions, and handle contextual interruptions such as inquiries about time, weather, or surroundings. These components paralleled the multimodal stimulation approaches shown to be most effective in robot-assisted interventions (Pennisi et al., 2016), demanding attentional shifting and cognitive flexibility as participants alternated between task-related and spontaneous conversational demands.

The decrease in number of therapist's prompts across training sessions (Fig. 4) indicates that most adolescents successfully navigated these transitions with minimal support, demonstrating increasing autonomy across sessions. These observations suggest the iCub robot served as an effective socially safe intermediary, allowing participants to rehearse complex cognitive and emotional responses relevant to real-life academic challenges. This aligns with Manzi et al.'s (2021) findings that humanoid robots with human-like gestures and morphology are particularly effective in fostering engagement in young adults, potentially facilitating better skill generalization to real-world academic contexts.

The absence of significant effects on cognitive measures may reflect several important considerations highlighted in the robot-assisted therapy literature. First, robot interventions show strongest effects for social-emotional outcomes rather than cognitive measures (Kouroupa et al., 2022), suggesting that the observed anxiety reduction may represent the primary therapeutic mechanism. Second, the heterogeneity of ASD presentations means that cognitive benefits may emerge more clearly in specific subgroups or with longer intervention periods (Hume et al., 2021). The preparatory demands of studying comics in advance may have introduced additional variability, as executive functioning challenges are common in ASD and can affect performance on structured cognitive tasks (Hume, 2014).

Nonetheless, the central goal of the training was to test feasibility of our approach and to offer to participants the repeated experience of managing an oral-exam-like situation with the robot across several weeks. This sustained exposure offered participants valuable opportunities to practice emotional regulation, attention shifting, and social communication in a structured, low-pressure context.

In conclusion, this study provides preliminary evidence that robot-assisted training may serve as a feasible and engaging complement to standard therapy for adolescents with ASD. The observed trend toward reduced anxiety and depression symptoms, though not statistically significant, suggests that robot-mediated interventions hold promise for supporting emotional resilience and cognitive skills during the challenging transition to adulthood for this population. However, larger-scale studies are required to clarify the potential of this promising intervention approach.

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